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Empowering perovskite modules for solar and indoor lighting applications by 1,8-diiodooctane/phenethylammonium iodide 2D perovskite passivation strategy

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ABSTRACT

To accelerate commercialization of perovskite technology and its use in multiple application fields, several device processing strategies have been developed. These efforts primarily target scaling-up device fabrication for mass production and enhancing performance for different light sources (sun or indoor light). This work presents a novel 3D/2D perovskite heterostructure by depositing a mixed layer of phenethylammonium iodide (PEAI) and 1,8-diiodooctane (DIO) directly atop the 3D perovskite absorber without a further annealing step. The addition of DIO enables the formation of pure 2D PEA₂PbI₄ (n = 1) at room temperature, leading to defect passivation of 3D perovskite surface, improvement in the crystallinity of 2D perovskite, and optimizing the dipole moment at perovskite/hole transport interface. Large-area PSC modules treated with PEAI:DIO achieve remarkable power conversion efficiencies of 17.7 % (32 cm²) and 15.6 % (121 cm²) under 1Sun irradiation. When exposed to indoor illumination with various LED intensities (200, 500 and 1000 lux) the PEAI:DIO engineered module demonstrated efficiency approaching 34 %, among the highest reported so far for large area modules employing perovskite with bandgap below 1.7 eV. Long-term stability tests following the ISOS-D-1 protocol reveal a threefold increase in T₈₀ lifetime compared to untreated devices.

1. Introduction

Hybrid organic-inorganic perovskites have attracted considerable interest in the field of photovoltaic (PV) devices due to their excellent and adjustable optoelectronic properties, ease of processability, low-temperature preparation, low cost and rapid increase in power conversion efficiency (PCE) [1,2]. Single-junction perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have now achieved a certified PCE of 27.1 %, according to the latest NREL efficiency chart and recent literature reports [3,4], while perovskite solar modules (PSMs) have reached 20.6 % with an aperture area of 215.53 cm² [3,5,6]. Furthermore, PSCs are emerging as a promise

technology for powering Internet-of-Things (IoT)-connected devices, given their broad absorption spectrum and tunable bandgap matching the indoor radiation spectrum [7]. The indoor PV market, valued at ~1200 billion USD in 2023 [8], is expected to grow, driven by demand for sustainable, maintenance-free power sources.

However, PSCs suffer from limited stability under humidity, temperature and light. Scaling up to larger modules often results in non-uniform perovskite active layer with an increased defect density, reducing PCE [9–11]. As a solution-processed technology, PSC quality is highly sensitive to deposition methods, processing conditions, and substrate size [12–15]. These defects contribute to significant structural

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imperfections, such as phase segregation, grain boundaries, and crystalline defects, which become more considerable at larger scales ($>1\text{ cm}^2$) [16] and in indoor conditions [17]. In the latter case, the low level of light intensity generates a much lower amount of excited charge carriers that cannot fill the traps, leading to an increase in the recombination rates and a decrease in the device fill factor (FF). Furthermore, poor contact between the perovskite layer and the electron transport layer (ETL) or the hole transport layer (HTL) further induces surface trap states, interfacial recombination, and hysteresis, limiting performance and stability [18–20]. Minimizing such defects and optimizing bandgap (E_g) are thus critical to improving indoor performance (iPCE) and enabling commercialization [21–24]. In particular, to optimize indoor light harvesting, bromine-rich wide-bandgap (WBG) perovskites are preferred, despite their tendency toward lower iPCE due to voltage losses from halide phase segregation and vacancy defects. Ma and co-workers addressed these issues by incorporating alkylamine oleylammonium ligands into a 2D/3D WBG perovskite ($\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.70}\text{MA}_{0.25}\text{PbI}_{2.25}\text{Br}_{0.75}$, $E_g = 1.71\text{ eV}$), achieving minimodules (12.18 cm^2) with 19.2% PCE under one-sun and a record 43.54% iPCE under 1000 lux warm-white LED [25].

Moreover Zhu and co-workers [26] demonstrated a flexible 24 cm^2 module with iPCEs of 30.73% and 26.48% under 1000 lux cold and warm white LEDs, respectively. Chang et al. also reported a 25 cm^2 AA module achieving iPCE=30.7% under T5 fluorescent lamp [27].

Additive engineering based on 2D materials is only one of several strategies to mitigate the defects limiting PSC performance. Other promising routes promote the use of functional 2D materials to passivate surface defects of the perovskite layer and its interface with charge transport layers [28–35]. Among them, graphene-based materials [36], transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) [37], transition metal carbides, nitrides, or carbonitrides (MXenes) [38] and 2D perovskites [39], stand out for their straightforward synthesis and remarkable chemical, electrical and physical properties.

In previous research, our group has demonstrated the potentialities of 2D materials in perovskite-based lab-scale devices [40,41], modules [42], panels [35] and even in perovskite-silicon tandem devices [43]. Specifically, graphene-doped mesoporous TiO_2 (m TiO_2 +G) acts as an effective template for the perovskite crystal growing [42], allowing for a fine control of the perovskite morphology even on large area substrates [44] while enlarging the device lifetime under operating conditions [45] due to the reduced trap state density at the m TiO_2 /perovskite interface [46]. Additionally, incorporating graphene flakes into the compact TiO_2 (c TiO_2 +G) hole blocking layer reduces the device dark current while improving the cell's FF [42]. This approach, allowed to realize large perovskite panels (0.5 m^2) connected in parallel, to form a solar farm (4.5 m^2) demonstrating excellent power stability in outdoor conditions [35].

A recent strategy to enhance PSC performance involves depositing organic halide salts like phenethylammonium iodide (PEAI) onto the 3D perovskite surface, forming a 2D PEA_2PbI_4 perovskite overlayer upon annealing, which improve environmental stability through defect passivation [47–54]. However, this 2D PEA_2PbI_4 overlayer limits charge transport due to its low in-plane mobility (10^{-2} – $10^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ V}^{-1}\text{ s}^{-1}$), [55–59]. and the bulky organic spacers in 3D/2D heterojunctions increase exciton binding energy, hindering charge carrier transport within the 2D layer and toward the hole transport layer in n-i-p PSCs [53].

Typically, these treatments yield mixed quasi-2D perovskite layers composed by various values of n (where n represents the number of inorganic slabs) with random orientation. Pursuing a pure $n = 1$ phase is desirable for optimal charge transfer and increased structural stability of 3D/2D heterostructure-based PSCs [60–62]. In case of PEAi precursor, quasi-2D phase is formed only upon a thermal annealing (around 100°C) usually showing a more likely mixture of phases ($n = 1$ and 2 phases) [63,64] that results in high charge recombination rates and reduced cell's V_{oc} [65].

To address these limitations, several strategies have been explored to

enhance 3D halide perovskites using 2D perovskites: (i) incorporating 2D perovskites into the 3D layer by adding organic spacer cations to the precursor solution or anti-solvent (surface gradient passivation) [66]; (ii) using isomers of 2D perovskite precursors to raise the energy barrier for 2D formation, preventing bulky organic cations from entering the perovskite lattice even at operating temperatures [55]; (iii) introducing a solvent dripping step after 2D perovskite deposition to create a phase-pure 2D ($n = 1$) region on the 3D perovskite surface [64]. While effective, these methods often increase device complexity and production costs, posing challenges for scalable, industrial-compatible fabrication [67–69].

Conversely, when PEAi is deposited without annealing, it forms a passivation layer that reduces defects, aligns work functions, and minimizes recombination at the perovskite/HTL interface, leading to high open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and improved device performance [52,53].

This approach is suitable under mild thermal conditions, as in indoor applications, where no additional thermal stress occurs.

However, without post-deposition annealing, the PEAi layer does not form a proper 3D/2D heterojunction, penalizing device stability under operative conditions. Notably, the use of PEAi and fluorinated derivatives (e.g., F-PEAI) has also proven effective in passivating perovskite films within the p-i-n architecture, as reported in recent literature [23,70], where enhanced stability, reduced trap states, and improved efficiency were demonstrated even under indoor illumination. These findings suggest that our PEAi:DIO-based strategy, which further improves coverage and surface passivation, could be extended to p-i-n configurations as well, thereby broadening its applicability across different device architectures.

In this work, we propose a novel PEAi-based passivation treatment for the perovskite surface enabling high performance large scale modules in both sun and indoor light conditions. In particular, we present a simple and innovative modification to the PEAi-based passivation layer by incorporating the 1,8-diiodooctane (DIO) additive within the PEAi precursor solution. Indeed, DIO is a well-established additive known for enhancing charge transport in both organic solar cells (OPVs) [71] and PSCs, where its use resulted in an improved perovskite layer crystallinity and coverage, as well as marked enhancements in PSC V_{oc} and PCE [72–74]. Here we found that the presence of DIO within the PEAi solution allowed to the formation of pure ($n = 1$) 2D PEA_2PbI_4 atop the 3D perovskite at room temperature, conjugating the main advantages of the improved structural stability typical for a 3D/2D heterostructure with the passivation effect of a PEAi-based treatment without applying any further post-deposition annealing step.

Our optimized 3D/2D perovskite heterostructure based on PEAi:DIO passivation treatment allowed us to fabricate highly efficient mesoscopic n-i-p (using graphene-doped ETL) devices based on $E_g = 1.63\text{ eV}$ perovskite ranging from small-scale cells (0.09 cm^2 and 0.5 cm^2), to larger areas modules (32 cm^2 and 121 cm^2 sizes). Moreover, the PEAi:DIO based 2D overlayer is effective in passivating 3D perovskite surface defects/vacancies by hampering the charge recombination and eventually boosting the device PCE, especially in case of indoor uses. The resulting PEAi:DIO based modules (active area 9 cm^2) demonstrate iPCE approaching 34% at 1000 lux (cold white LED, 6500 K), retaining iPCE near 30% at very low illuminance (200 lux), without the need to use WBG perovskite formulation. This work paves the way for facile scaling up of perovskite devices based on 3D/2D heterostructure with minimal impact on device production costs, while promoting the next commercialization of versatile and efficient technology for both solar and indoor lighting applications.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Fluorine-doped tin oxide (FTO - $7\ \Omega\ \text{sq}^{-1}$) glass substrates were purchased from Pilkington. Anhydrous solvents (dimethyl formamide –

DMF, dimethyl sulfoxide – DMSO, acetonitrile – ACN, chlorobenzene – CB, isopropyl alcohol – IPA, ethanol – EtOH and, acetylacetonate), 4-*tert*-butylpyridine (tBP; 98%), Lithium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl) imide (LiTFSI; 99.95%), 1,8-Diiodooctane (DIO) and, titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Phenethylammonium iodide iodide (PEAI), formamidinium iodide (FAI), methylammonium bromide (MABr), and tris(2-(1H-pyrazol-1-yl)-4-*tert*-butylpyridine)cobalt(III)tris(bis(trifluoromethylsulfonyl)imide (FK209 Co(III)TFSI), and TiO₂ paste (30 N-RD) were acquired from Great Cell Solar LTD. Lead iodide (PbI₂, >99%), cesium iodide (CsI, 99.9%), and lead bromide (PbBr₂, >98%) were acquired from Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI) America, Inc. 2,2',7,7'-tetrakis [N, N-di(4-methoxyphenyl) amino] 9,9'-spirobifluorene (spiro-OMeTAD, 99.8%) was purchased from Xi'an Polymer Light Technology in China. Hellmanex was purchased from Hellma Analytics. All materials were used as received.

2.2. Device fabrication methods

The n-i-p-type perovskite solar cells and modules with architecture Glass/c-TiO₂:Graphene/meso-TiO₂:Graphene/CsFAMA(Cs_{0.05}FA_{0.85}MA_{0.10}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.17})₃)/PEAI or PEAI:DIO/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au were made in different sizes: 2.5 cm × 2.5 cm (four 0.09 cm² active area devices or one 0.5 cm² active area device; the active area is defined by a mask during the measurement), 5.6 cm × 5.6 cm module (9 cm² active area, 5 sub-cells) and 11 cm × 11 cm module (45 cm² active area, 15 sub-cells). FTO is patterned (P1) by a Nd:YVO₄ laser system (Explorer One HP 355-4), λ = 355 nm, pulsed at 80 kHz, fluence = 10.2 J/cm², in order to form the series connected cells. Glass/FTO patterned substrates were cleaned in an ultrasonic bath with Hellmanex 2% solution for 25 min at room temperature, followed by water, and isopropyl alcohol for 10 min each. Then, the FTO substrates were dried under nitrogen gas flow and treated in a UV-Ozone chamber for 30 min. A hot plate was used to heat the substrates to 460 °C. The compact TiO₂ layer (c-TiO₂+Graphene) was deposited by spray pyrolysis from a solution containing 18 mL of ethanol, 0.8 mL of acetylacetonate and 1.2 mL of titanium diisopropoxide bis(acetylacetonate) doped with graphene flakes solution (1 vol%) [42] in cycles of 20 s between each deposition [35]. This amount of the c-TiO₂+Graphene solution was sufficient to coat an FTO surface of approximately 15 × 15 cm². After spraying, the substrates were kept at 460 °C for 15 min. The c-TiO₂+Graphene substrates at 150 °C, were immediately transferred to the UV Ozone chamber for 30 min. The mesoporous TiO₂ layer (m-TiO₂+Graphene) was deposited by spin-coating at 4000 rpm (2 s ramp up) for 30 s using a solution containing 150 mg of TiO₂ paste (30 N-RD) in 1 mL of ethanol with graphene flakes solution (1 vol%) [35]. Subsequently, the substrates (Glass/FTO/c-TiO₂+Graphene/m-TiO₂+Graphene) were sintered in multiple temperature steps as reported by Araújo and co-workers [13]. CsFAMA perovskite layer was deposited by spin coating using CB as anti-solvent in an inert atmosphere of N₂. In SI section S1.1, Table S1 shows the parameters deposition for the perovskite layer according to the size of the substrate by following the upscaling optimization reported here [75]. After deposition, the perovskite layer was annealed at 100 °C for 1 h. Then, a PEAI or PEAI:DIO passivating layer was deposited. PEAI and PEAI:DIO passivation solutions (see SI section S1.2, Table S2) were spin-coated at 3000 rpm for 30 s (0 s ramp up) on top of perovskite film in dynamic mode, without any further annealing step. The hole transport layer (HTL) was prepared using a Spiro-OMeTAD solution made with a concentration of 70 mM (100 mg mL⁻¹) in chlorobenzene with the addition (additives) of 36 μL of tBP, 20 μL of Li-TFSI solution (520 mg/mL in ACN), 8 μL of FK209 solution (375.8 mg/mL in ACN). The spiro-OMeTAD solution was deposited on the top passivation layer at 4000 rpm for 20 s (dynamic mode). In the case of the modules, the next step is the removal by laser ablation the full stack deposited on FTO from the vertical connection areas to series connect two adjacent cells with the subsequent electrode deposition. P2 parameters are

optimized as follows: λ = 355 nm, Nd:YVO₄ pulsed at 80 kHz, fluence = 210 cm. The characterization about the quality of the P2 is reported in [75]. Before the deposition of the counter electrode, the samples were left overnight in a desiccator with silica gel beads protected from light and humidity. Finally, the gold counter electrode was deposited by thermal evaporation in a two-step process: the first 20 nm at 0.1 Å/s and then at 1.0 Å/s up to 80 nm. P3 process is implemented to remove carefully the metal electrode and get the series connections among the cells (λ = 355 nm, Nd:YVO₄ pulsed at 80 kHz, fluence = 195 cm²)

2.3. Optoelectronic and morphological characterizations

UV-Vis absorption spectra of the perovskite films were acquired using an Agilent spectrophotometer, model Cary 60, in the 200–1000 nm range. Field Emission Gun Scanning Electron Microscopy (FEG-SEM) images were obtained using a Quanta FEG 250 microscope (FEI Co, USA) coupled with field emission gun and were collected to investigate surface morphologies of the samples (homogeneity and grain perovskite size). The KPFM images were obtained simultaneously using a Flex AFM with a C3000 controller (Nanosurf, Switzerland), operating under dry atmosphere and with a Pt/Ir coated tip (EFM tip, Nanoworld, Switzerland), resonance frequency of 75 kHz and a force constant of 2.8 N m⁻¹. X-ray diffraction measurements (XRD) were registered in Bruker Phaser D2 diffractometer with Cu Kα radiation (λ = 1.5418 Å), using θ-2θ geometry, varying 2θ from 2° to 45° with a step of 0.02° and 0.4 s. Photoluminescence spectra measurements (PL) were performed in an Ocean Optics QEPro spectrofluorometer with a 365 nm LED as an excitation light source (2.6 mW cm⁻²) directly on the surface of the films. Current-Voltage (J-V) curves of the PSCs and PSMs were measured in ambient air and under the illumination of 1 Sun (100 mW/cm²) using a class A Solar Simulator (Air Mass 1.5 G filter, ABET Sun 2000). The light intensity was calibrated using a reference silicon solar cell (RERA Solutions RR-1002). Active areas of 0.09 cm² (small cell) and 0.5 cm² (large area cell) were determined by a black mask. An optical power density-based measurement system (Arkeo-Cicci research s.r.l.) was used to realize the measures of transient photovoltage (TPV) decay and external quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra. Indoor J-V curves of devices with and without modifications were acquired under a cold white LED source (Beghelli, 50 W, daylight 6500k). The stability tests were made according to ISOS protocols (International Summit on Organic Photovoltaic Stability) without any encapsulation [76].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of the 3D/2D perovskite films

To investigate the impact of the DIO-modified PEAI passivation layer, a comprehensive set of morphological and spectroscopic characterizations such as UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy, steady-state photoluminescence (PL), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) measurements were performed on the surface of Cs_{0.05}FA_{0.85}MA_{0.10}Pb(I_{0.83}Br_{0.17})₃ perovskite films (CsFAMA). These analyses can reveal critical modifications that can significantly enhance photovoltaic performance parameters, including V_{oc}, J_{sc}, FF and ultimately, PCE. The films were treated with different concentrations (1% and 3%) of DIO-modified PEAI. Detailed methods for the preparation of the perovskite films, PEAI solutions, and deposition conditions can be found in the Supporting Information (SI, Table S2).

The UV-Vis absorption spectra of perovskite films without and with the passivation layer (PEAI and PEAI:DIO) are shown in Fig. 1a. All films exhibited a consistent absorption peak around 740 nm, with no notable differences in other spectral regions [77].

The structural changes in the passivation layer of the perovskite were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements (Fig. 1b), and detailed XRD 2θ < 13° is shown in Fig. 1c, acquired on the photo-electrode. The XRD pattern reveals that perovskite films passivated with

Fig. 1. a-d) UV-Vis absorption spectra, XRD patterns and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of the CsFAMA films without (wo/PEAI) or with passivation layer (PEAI, PEAI:1 %DIO, and PEAI:3 %DIO v/v), respectively. All films were prepared by spin coating on glass substrates or meso-TiO₂:graphene/c-TiO₂:graphene/FTO/glass substrates. SEM images were acquired at 2 kV. Figs. 1e) and 1f) present steady-state photoluminescence (PL) spectra of Glass/CsFAMA perovskite films with different surface modifications, comparing results without annealing (1e) and with annealing at 100°C for 6 min (1f).

non-annealed PEAI exhibit distinct peaks characteristic of 2D PEA_2PbI_4 at approximately 5.4 $^\circ$ and 10.8 $^\circ$ [78,79] (see SI, section S3, Figure S1 for both non-annealed PEAI and PEAI:DIO films deposited on FTO/glass and PVK/FTO/glass substrates). Notably, the intensity of these peaks is significantly enhanced in perovskite/PEAI:DIO films, with the intensity increasing as the DIO content in the 2D PEA_2PbI_4 layer increases. This enhancement indicates that the 2D passivation layer containing DIO achieves greater crystallinity and a more ordered structure compared to the pure PEAI layer. This observation confirms the successful formation of a 2D PEA_2PbI_4 overlayer atop the 3D perovskite in both samples. Other peaks correspond to the planes of CsFAMA perovskite (#) [80], PbI_2 at 12.7 $^\circ$, and the TiO₂ and FTO substrates [52,53]. The morphology

of the perovskite layers was investigated using SEM images, as presented in Fig. 1d. The images reveal distinct surface characteristics that vary between perovskite films passivated with PEAI and those modified with DIO. The PEAI:DIO treated perovskite films exhibit uniform pinholes-free coverage, characterized by square-shaped grains [81]. Square-shaped perovskite grains in SEM images can indicate improved film quality, leading to enhanced solar cell performance [82]. Their uniform packing minimizes voids and structural defects, reducing non-radiative recombination losses at grain boundaries. This morphology also facilitates better charge transport, contributing to higher efficiency. Additionally, the compact and ordered structure improves the stability of the material, mitigating degradation due to

environmental factors. These characteristics make square-shaped grains a desirable feature for optimizing perovskite solar cell performance and longevity. It is important to point out that in the SEM images for the perovskite/PEAI:DIO films in comparison with perovskite films without and with PEAI, there is no evidence of bright grains that are usually attributed to the presence of large lead iodide clusters [83].

The photoluminescence (PL) spectra, in Figs. 1e and 1f, highlighted the beneficial role of DIO in the PEAI layer, showing how its inclusion promotes the self-arising formation of a 2D passivation layer while influencing the perovskite structure and enhancing its optoelectronic properties. The strong peak at 1.604 eV corresponds to 3D perovskite emission in all samples, with a noticeably higher intensity in PEAI:DIO films compared to the reference, indicating improved passivation and reduced non-radiative recombination [53]. Moreover, the DIO-doped PEAI films showed a blue-shifted emission peak at 1.619 eV across all doping percentages (1 % and 3 %) with a narrower emission bandwidth. This blue-shift, as reported in the literature [84,85], can be correlated with trap state filling on the surface of the perovskite film induced by the passivation layer.

Notably, in the absence of annealing (Fig. 1e), the PL spectra are dominated by a prominent emission peak at approximately 2.4 eV, corresponding to the formation of a pure 2D perovskite $n = 1$ phase. This outcome is particularly desirable, as the $n = 1$ phase is associated with superior exciton confinement, enhanced moisture resistance, and effective passivation, all of which contribute to improved device stability and efficiency. The lack of additional peaks suggests that the PEAI:DIO layer preserves a well-defined 2D structure without significant intermixing with the underlying 3D perovskite or different mixed phases, reinforcing its role in achieving a high-quality passivation layer. On the contrary, upon annealing at 100°C for six minutes, distinct differences emerge in the PL response of PEAI-only and PEAI:DIO-treated films, suggesting an induced structural transformation, as evidenced by the appearance of additional peaks at approximately 2.2 eV and 2.0 eV, which are attributed to the formation of $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ quasi-2D phases, respectively. (Fig. 1f). These mixed-dimensional phases suggest a partial degradation of the pure $n = 1$ structure and the development of a more disordered heterostructure. More in detail, the PEAI-only sample shows reduced PL intensity at the 3D perovskite emission (~1.65 eV), indicating poor passivation and increased non-radiative recombination due to structural inhomogeneity and interdiffusion of PEAI. In contrast, films treated with PEAI:DIO, particularly at 3 % DIO, exhibit stronger PL at ~1.65 eV, suggesting more effective passivation retained after annealing. This is attributed to DIO's role in modulating crystallization and improving PEAI distribution, thereby suppressing trap states and enhancing interface quality.

A key observation is the inversion in the relative PL intensities of the $n = 1$ (~2.4 eV) and 3D (~1.65 eV) peaks. In the PEAI-only film, the 3D emission dominates, indicating incomplete or unstable $n = 1$ phase formation. In contrast, the PEAI:DIO (3 %) film exhibits a dominant $n = 1$ peak, demonstrating that DIO promotes and stabilizes the formation of a pure 2D perovskite phase even after thermal treatment. While annealing introduces minor contributions from $n = 2$ and $n = 3$ phases, it is important to note that the formation of a well-defined 2D perovskite structure, particularly the pure $n = 1$ phase, typically requires thermal activation. In this context, the key innovation of our work lies in achieving a stable $n = 1$ 2D perovskite phase at room temperature, eliminating the need for thermal annealing.

The formation of a quasi-2D perovskite with multiple dimensional phases could compromise the advantages of the pure $n = 1$ phase by introducing an increased disorder and altering the charge transport properties. Although quasi-2D perovskites can still offer good performance, the presence of mixed-dimensional phases may lead to less controlled film morphology and potential stability issues. Therefore, the results strongly suggest that maintaining the pure $n = 1$ perovskite phase, as observed without annealing in the presence of DIO, is the most favorable outcome for optimizing 3D/2D perovskite heterostructure.

3.2. Photovoltaic performance

We examined the effect of DIO additive in the 2D PEAI passivation layer on the photovoltaic parameters and stability of n-i-p PSCs and PSMs. The schematic illustration of the mesoporous architecture of the devices is indicated in Fig. 2a, while the cross-sectional SEM images of the as realized layered structure are shown in Fig. 2b. Finally, in Fig. 2c the reported pictures of the different sizes of the devices highlight the successful fabrication of devices ranging from small-scale prototypes to significantly larger substrates, showcasing the versatility and scalability of the manufacturing process developed in this work. This adaptability is critical for advancing technology towards practical applications, as it bridges the PCE gap between laboratory-scale research and industrial-scale production.

Photovoltaic devices (Glass/c-TiO₂:Graphene/meso-TiO₂:Graphene/CsFAMA/ PEAI or PEAI: DIO/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au) with and without 2D passivation strategy were prepared as described in the **Experimental Section**. Furthermore, we used our already established protocol for graphene-doped TiO₂ layer [45], which guarantees enhanced perovskite crystal quality, reduced trap state density, improved interfacial stability, decreased dark current, ultimately resulting in an overall increased fill factor (FF). The CsFAMA active layer surface was modified with PEAI in IPA as control device and with the incorporation of, 1 %, 3 % and 5 % of DIO (perovskite post-deposition treatment) inside the PEAI solution, according to the mixtures described in Table S2. Fig. 3a-b show the J-V curves under full sunlight (100 mA cm⁻²), IPCE measurements and integrated J_{sc} (derived from the IPCE spectra) for the best devices with an active area of 0.09 cm². Statistics of photovoltaic characteristic parameters for PSCs are reported in Fig. 3c-f, while the photovoltaic parameter values for champion devices for each modification are reported in Table 1.

According to Fig. 3 (c-f) the PSC using as interfacial engineering a PEAI:3 %DIO passivation layer, showed increased V_{oc} up to 1.13 V, FF up to 80.00 %, J_{sc} up to 22.40 mA cm⁻² respectively, reflecting in an enhanced PCE of 20.25 %. Conversely, the best PEAI control device demonstrates a PCE of 18.45 %, with a V_{oc} of 1.07 V, J_{sc} of 21.81 mA cm⁻², and an FF of 79.07 %. The reduction of cell performance once PEAI:5 %DIO modification is used, can be confidently ascribed with a saturation in 2D PEAI charge mobility due to the excess of DIO additive reflecting in a cell FF reduction (no evident morphological and structural changes are observed for PEAI:5 %DIO samples with respect to PEAI:3 %DIO samples, as shown in Figure S2 in SI). In particular, the PEAI:3 %DIO cell V_{oc} shows a 60 mV improvement compared to PSC control devices. This enhanced V_{oc} performance, can be confidently attributed to the more efficient charge extraction at the perovskite/HTL heterojunction interface and reduced charge recombination losses, as supported by the PL measurements presented in Fig. 1b. Hysteresis behavior reveals a clear trend across the different passivation strategies, as reflected in the changes in power conversion efficiency (PCE) between forward (FW) and reverse (RV) scans (see Table 1). The reference PEAI sample shows moderate hysteresis, with PCE increasing from 17.06 % to 17.76 %. With 1 % DIO, hysteresis remains comparable (17.97–18.68 %), suggesting only a marginal effect. However, in the case of 3 % DIO, hysteresis is significantly reduced, with PCE rising from 19.25 % to 19.76 %, indicating improved interfacial charge dynamics. At 5 % DIO, although V_{oc} remains stable, hysteresis becomes more pronounced again (17.24–18.4 %), possibly due to morphological or interfacial degradation. These findings underscore the importance of optimizing DIO concentration, with 3 % offering the most effective balance for mitigating hysteresis in perovskite solar cells.

To further confirm the suppressed non-radiative recombination in the perovskite layer, we performed the time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) spectroscopy measurements (Fig. 4a). The average lifetime (τ_{avg}) was determined through the fitted curve data using a double exponential equation, resulting in two different time constants (Table S3) [86]. The perovskite/PEAI:3 %DIO film, with a more

Fig. 2. a) Schematic of the n-i-p PSC structure using DIO-modified PEAI as 2D passivation layer; the molecular structures of phenethylammonium iodide (PEAI) salt and 1,8-diiodooctane (DIO) additive are indicated in the dark pink circle. b) Cross-section SEM image of the investigated structure: glass/c-TiO₂:G/m-TiO₂:G/CsFAMA/PEAI:DIO. c) Pictures of the perovskite-based devices (PSCs and PSMs) of different sizes.

extended average lifetime ($\tau_{\text{avg}} = 847$ ns) compared to the perovskite/PEAI film ($\tau_{\text{avg}} = 780$ ns), indicates that the 2D PEAI:DIO passivation layer effectively mitigates trap states in the perovskite film [86], consistent with improved surface passivation and interface quality. This result was also confirmed by transient photovoltage (TPV) measurements [87], as shown in Fig. 4b. PV measurements probe the recombination dynamics in complete devices under open-circuit conditions. The decay time extracted from TPV reflects the lifetime of photogenerated carriers: a slower decay (i.e., longer TPV lifetime) indicates reduced recombination and more efficient charge retention within the device. In fact, the perovskite device with modified PEAI:3 % DIO layer exhibited a longer carrier recombination lifetime, indicating slower recombination kinetics and a suppressed non-radiative recombination pathways in the perovskite film [88]. These longer lifetimes correlate with the enhanced photovoltaic parameters observed, particularly the V_{OC} and FF, as they are both sensitive to recombination losses. The results support the conclusion that the PEAI:DIO treatment contributes to enhanced device performance by extending carrier lifetimes and stabilizing the interfacial energetics. The charge recombination dynamics of PSCs were also studied by measurements of the J_{SC} vs. light intensity as reported in Fig. 4c showing the linear fitting between J_{SC} and intensity data. By fitting the log-log plot J_{SC} vs. intensity (Sun) values to a power function, described as $J_{\text{SC}} \propto P_{\text{light}}^{\alpha}$, it is possible to obtain the α value. The α is the exponent indicating the nature of charge carrier recombination and transport processes [89]. As shown in Fig. 4c, the PEAI and PEAI:3 %DIO devices exhibited α values of 0.95 and 0.96,

respectively. A higher value of exponent α , approaching 1, obtained for PEAI:DIO device, suggests that carrier charge transfer to the corresponding charge transport layer occurs more efficiently, underscoring the 2D passivation layer's effectiveness in minimizing carrier recombination [90]. In particular, the passivation mechanism of PEA^+ cations and I^- anions involves interaction with iodine atoms of the DIO additive ($\text{I}(\text{CH}_2)_8$) through halogen bonding, effectively neutralizing surface defects in the CsFAMA film, such as iodine vacancies, and uncoordinated Pb by improving the photovoltaic performance of the PSCs [91].

Kelvin probe force microscopy (KPFM) was used to investigate the electrical properties of 3D/2D perovskite heterojunctions [92]. In particular, the contrast in the CPD map in dark indicates an uneven distribution of permanent charges [93], and permanently trapped charge carriers [94]. Moreover, KPFM measurements determine the contact potential difference (CPD) mapping of the CsFAMA/PEAI and CsFAMA/PEAI:3 %DIO films, as shown in Fig. 4d-e deposited on Glass/FTO/m-TiO₂:G/c-TiO₂:G substrates, as in case of a PSC photoelectrode. According to the CPD mapping statistics extracted from the KPFM measurements (Fig. 4e), the perovskite film passivated with PEAI:3 %DIO exhibited a higher average surface potential (0.88 V) than the film passivated with only PEAI (0.73 V). According to the literature, this increase in the CPD suggests that in the dark condition, the trap states density of the PEAI:3 %DIO sample is significantly reduced with respect to the control PEAI one [94]. Moreover, the higher CPD (and thus higher WF) [95] observed in case of PEAI:3 %DIO sample could be also indicative of an increased band bending at perovskite/PEAI:3 %DIO

Fig. 3. a) J - V curves of the champion PSCs were obtained (1 Sun illumination) at the forward scan (FW, dotted line) and the reverse scan (RV, solid line). The inset in the JV graphic is a photo of a sample containing 4 small area PSCs (active area of 0.09 cm). b) External quantum efficiency (IPCE) spectra for the best-efficient PSCs. The photovoltaic performance statistics for PEAI (pink), PEAI:1 %DIO (orange) and PEAI:3 %DIO (blue) and PEAI:5 %DIO (green) devices are reported in panel c) Open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}), d) short-circuit current density (J_{sc}), e) fill factor (FF) and f) power conversion efficiency (PCE) in case of FW (squares) and RV (circles) scans. See Fig. S3 for a detailed discussion for devices without interfacial passivation.

Table 1

Summary of the average values of photovoltaic parameters (V_{oc} , J_{sc} , FF, and PCE) for reverse (RV) and forward (FW) scans and integrated J_{sc} for each modification of mesoporous architecture devices. Small area PSCs have an active area of 0.09 cm. The values in parenthesis are for the best-performing devices.

Passivation	Scan	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	PCE (%)	Integrated J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)
PEAI	FW	1.06 ± 0.01 (1.06)	21.63 ± 0.22 (21.86)	74.79 ± 0.78 (75.39)	17.06 ± 0.35 (17.63)	21.30
	RV	1.06 ± 0.01 (1.07)	21.70 ± 0.23 (21.81)	77.80 ± 0.71 (79.07)	17.76 ± 0.38 (18.45)	
PEAI:1 % DIO	FW	1.11 ± 0.02 (1.11)	21.83 ± 0.34 (21.96)	75.42 ± 1.33 (73.67)	17.97 ± 0.57 (17.96)	21.70
	RV	1.11 ± 0.02 (1.11)	21.84 ± 0.32 (22.04)	76.88 ± 1.54 (78.00)	18.68 ± 0.55 (19.15)	
PEAI:3 % DIO	FW	1.13 ± 0.01 (1.12)	22.17 ± 0.31 (22.33)	77.66 ± 1.02 (77.19)	19.25 ± 0.26 (19.42)	22.85
	RV	1.13 ± 0.01 (1.13)	22.18 ± 0.30 (22.40)	79.07 ± 0.69 (80.00)	19.76 ± 0.35 (20.25)	
PEAI:5 % DIO	FW	1.13 ± 0.01 (1.13)	21.37 ± 0.43 (21.97)	72.33 ± 2.07 (75.09)	17.24 ± 0.69 (18.64)	21.36
	RV	1.13 ± 0.01 (1.13)	21.33 ± 0.44 (21.98)	76.12 ± 1.44 (78.12)	18.40 ± 0.59 (19.48)	

*Average and standard deviation values were obtained on 12 devices.

interface that facilitates charge injection and separation processes at perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD interface [96] once cell is working under illumination.

In addition, the CPD of the PEAI:3 %DIO sample is more homogeneous than the control sample as shown from the full-width half maximum value (FWHM) of the sample's CPD histogram distribution in the dark, see Fig. 4e. Higher fluctuations in the CPD distribution map of the PEAI reference sample refer to a higher density of point defects [95].

Therefore, KPFM measurements suggested that DIO plays a double role when added to PEAI. First, DIO efficiently passivates defects atop the perovskite surface due to the halogen bonding that can occur between the iodine atom of DIO and the under-coordinated Pb^{2+} or I^- sites. This passivation reduces the electronic disorder, resulting in a higher and more uniform surface potential. Secondly, DIO modifies the PEAI dipole (due to its ammonium group ($-NH_4^+$) and iodide ion (I^-)), resulting in a higher surface potential of the PEAI:3 %DIO sample.

Fig. 4. **a)** Time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) of the CsFAMA perovskite films passivated with PEAI and 3 % DIO-doped PEAI. **b)** Recombination time measured from fitting the transient photovoltage (TPV) and **c)** Average J_{sc} versus light intensity of devices using CsFAMA perovskite as active layer, PEAI passivated and PEAI doped with 3 % DIO. Error bars represent the standard deviation of the data. α values were extracted by individually fitting the J_{sc} vs. light intensity curve for each device, followed by calculating the average and standard deviation to assess consistency across the batch. **d)** KPFM merged images (scale bar of the 500 nm) of the perovskite film passivated with PEAI and PEAI:3 %DIO. **e)** Statistical distributions of KPFM images.

Furthermore, XRD measurements (Fig. 1b-c) indicate that adding DIO enhances the crystallinity of the 2D perovskite layer, as evidenced by narrower and more intense diffraction peaks as the DIO percentual increases. This trend is further supported by the FWHM values, which decreases from 0.35 for PEAI to 0.14 with 1 % DIO-doped PEAI and further to 0.12 with 3 % DIO-doped PEAI (Fig. 1c), confirming improved crystallinity with higher DIO content. This improvement is likely attributed to the interaction between iodine in DIO and iodide ions (I^-) in PEAI, which reduces the crystallization kinetics of the 2D perovskite, leading to improved film quality [73,74,97]. As a result, a more ordered crystal structure is formed, significantly enhancing both the optoelectronic properties and morphology of the 2D perovskite layer, as evidenced by PL measurements (Fig. 1e-f) and XRD measurements (Fig. 1b-c).

To gain a deeper understanding of the role of the DIO additive, we explored the interaction between the perovskite surface and the passivation layer using ab-initio simulations. Specifically, we modelled a pseudo-cubic $MAPbI_3$ perovskite slab exposing its PbI_2 -terminated surface, incorporating an iodine vacancy (V_I) at the interface with the passivation layer. The details of the simulated structure and computational accuracy are provided in the SI (section S5, Figure S5).

Figs. 5a and 5b illustrate the optimized configurations of the perovskite/PEAI and perovskite/DIO interfaces, respectively. At both interfaces, the iodine atom of the passivation molecule forms a covalent

bond with the under-coordinated Pb atom on the perovskite surface, effectively stabilizing the system, as demonstrated by the negative adsorption energy reported in Fig. 5. This is confirmed by the projected density of states (PDOS) analysis showing the capabilities of DIO in passivating the V_I defect states are significant. Specifically, Fig. 5c presents the Projected Density of States (PDOS) for the perovskite surface containing V_I defects, where the defect states, primarily contributed by under-coordinated Pb ions (highlighted in red), are clearly visible. However, as shown in Fig. 5d, these defect states are significantly suppressed when the surface interacts with the DIO passivation molecule.

However, the DFT analyses show additional benefit in using DIO. In fact, the charge transfer between the perovskite and the passivation molecules exhibits opposite signs for PEAI and DIO, leading to interface dipoles with opposite orientations, as shown in Figs. 5a and 5b. In particular, the interface dipole induced by the DIO interaction causes a relative downshift of the perovskite energy levels with respect to HTL. While this shift enhances hole extraction, ultimately improving the FF, the passivation effect leads to a noticeable increase in V_{OC} , as further discussed in the SI (see Figures S6 and S7 respectively).

The double role of DIO confirmed by the DFT simulations is mainly reflected in the improved electrical parameters obtained in the PEAI:3 % DIO PSC performance already shown in Fig. 3. In particular, an improvement in V_{OC} is mainly related to the passivation effect, while modification of the electrical dipole at perovskite/spiro-OMeTAD

Fig. 5. relaxed configuration of **a)** perovskite/PEAI interface and **b)** perovskite/DIO interface. The related adsorption energy (E_{ADS}) and charge transfer on the passivation molecule (Δq) are reported, along with the direction of the resulting interface dipole. **c)** PDOS of the perovskite surface with iodine vacancy (VI) defect states. **d)** PDOS of the perovskite surface with VI defects interacting with the DIO passivation molecule. The states contributed by the under-coordinated Pb atom at the interface with the passivation layer are depicted in red.

increases the device FF values (for further details, see Supporting Information S5).

Moreover, the formation of a 3D/2D heterostructure induced by the DIO additive in PEAI reflected in an improved shelf-life stability, as reported in Figure S8. We performed these stability tests following the ISOS-D-1 protocol [95], by storing the PSCs without encapsulation in dark and ambient conditions, maintaining a relative humidity of approximately $55 \pm 3\%$ [76]. The optimized device showed a T_{80} (time span in which the device retains more than 80% of its initial PCE) of 1600 h, almost three times longer than that one showed by reference PEAI cell. This significant enhancement highlights the critical role of integrating the DIO-based 2D PEA_2PbI_4 layer, which effectively enhances the robustness of the devices in ambient environment. Moreover, we also assessed short-term operational stability under continuous 1 SUN illumination following the ISOS-L1 protocol (see Figure S9 and section S6 for further details). Both PEAI and PEAI:3% DIO not encapsulated devices compared to the PEAI:3% DIO counterpart, suggesting DIO not only facilitates high-quality 2D layer formation but may also contribute to mitigating the rapid degradation typically seen in non-annealed PEAI-treated devices [53].

Based on our findings with small-area PSCs, we demonstrated that the incorporation of a 2D passivation layer, formed by blending DIO and PEAI and depositing it onto the CsFAMA perovskite film, creates a strongly favorable interface, achieving remarkable V_{OC} and PCE values. To investigate whether the 2D PEAI:DIO passivation layer can maintain its ability to passivate surface defects at the perovskite/HTL interface under upscaling conditions, we fabricated large-area modules with substrate dimensions of 32 cm^2 and 121 cm^2 , as shown in Fig. 6. To scale-up to module size, we have optimized the PVSF composition, and the spin-coating ramping, speed and timing (see Table S1) for both PVSF solution and antisolvent.

Fig. 6 shows the photographs and I-V curves of the best large-area devices for all active area sizes under full sunlight (1 Sun), using PEAI

and PEAI:3% DIO surface treatment, while the electrical parameters are reported in Table 2.

The enhancement of the photovoltaic parameters, V_{OC} , FF, and PCE were observed with the PEAI:3% DIO 2D passivation layer across all device sizes. Notably, in large area PSCs, the PEAI:3% DIO 2D passivation layer led to substantial improvements in V_{OC} and FF, achieving values of 1.13 V and 75.23%, respectively. These results outperformed those obtained with the PEAI passivation layer, which yielded V_{OC} and FF values of 1.07 V and 68.05%, respectively. This highlights the effectiveness of this novel 2D passivation strategy, even when the device is scaled up. The improved deposition strategy, PEAI:DIO passivation and the optimization of cells interconnection resulted in the fabrication of PSMs, where the PEAI:3% DIO modified device achieved PCEs 17.68% (5.80 V of V_{OC}) and 15.05% (17.00 V of V_{OC}) on 32 cm^2 and 45 cm^2 active areas, respectively. Forward and reverse J-V scans were performed on the 5 sub-cell modules to assess hysteresis behavior at the larger scale, representative of practical device areas. As shown in Table S6 and the corresponding J-V curves in Figure S10, the PEAI:3% DIO-modified modules exhibit improved photovoltaic performance and reduced hysteresis compared to the PEAI-only devices. These results confirm that the trends observed at the cell level extend to larger-area devices, indicating enhanced interfacial quality and more stable charge extraction with DIO incorporation. Moreover, the reduced hysteresis observed in both cells and modules also suggests that the incorporation of DIO may contribute to more stable interfacial properties, which could play a role in limiting early-stage performance losses typically associated with burn-in degradation reported for devices employing PEAI passivation without annealing [53], which is particularly relevant under elevated temperature conditions. The ability to manufacture devices on larger substrates not only ensures higher throughput but also paves the way for broader integration into commercial systems, further emphasizing the innovation and scalability achieved in this study.

Fig. 6. J - V or I - V obtained (1 Sun illumination) under RV voltage scan and related pictures curves of champion devices with different active area sizes (a)-0.5 cm²; b)-9cm²; c)-45 cm²); pink curves are related to PEAI devices while blue curves are related to PEAI:3 %DIO devices.

Table 2

Photovoltaic parameters for large-area PSCs and PSMs.

Device	Passivation	Substrate area (cm ²)	Active area (cm ²)	V _{oc} (V)	I _{sc} (mA)	FF (%)	PCE(%)
Large area PSC	PEAI	6.25	0.5	1.07	10.29	68.05	14.98
	PEAI:3 %DIO			1.13	10.46	75.23	17.79
PSM 5 sub-cells	PEAI	32	9	5.77	36.42	73.35	17.07
	PEAI:3 %DIO			5.80	36.18	75.96	17.68
Big-PSM 15 sub-cells	PEAI	121	45	16.37	59.17	65.44	14.09
	PEAI:3 %DIO			16.95	60.16	68.74	15.58

3.3. Indoor measurements

When considering low levels of light intensity, defects present in the perovskite layer such as grain boundaries or halide vacancies strongly hamper the charge dynamics, since the low amount of excited charge

carriers cannot effectively fill the traps, leading to an increased charge recombination rates and eventually penalized FF. Our findings demonstrated that the strategy of incorporating DIO as an additive within the PEAI solution leads to PSCs and PSMs that deliver high performance under standard 1 Sun condition (100 mW cm⁻²). To further assess the

Fig. 7. a) Schematic illustration of the PSM indoor measurement conditions. b) J-V curves under LED illumination with different intensities (200 lux, 500 lux and 1000 lux) of the PSM (5 sub-cells in series, 9 cm² active area) using PEAI:3 % DIO as 2D passivation layer. c) Photovoltaic parameters of the as-realized PSM.

potential integration of these devices into low-power electronics for indoor environments, we performed JV measurements under low-intensity illumination on a module (PEAI:3 %DIO) with an active area of 9 cm². We selected as main indoor source a cold white LED (6500 K) since the white light source is the most common lighting source for indoor scenes, while the warm white light source is a dedicated light source in the semiconductor manufacturing industry or home lighting [98]. The spectral irradiance of the white LED is reported in SI section S7 Figure S11 for 1000, 500 and 200 lux illuminance.

Fig. 7 shows a schematic illustration of PSM indoor measurement conditions, J-V curves of the PSM (5 sub-cells in series) using PEAI:3 % DIO as a 2D passivation layer acquired under illumination using a cool-white led lamp at 1000 lux, 500 lux and 200 lux, respectively. The illuminance was calibrated by using a NIST-traceable calibrated Digisense 20250–00 luxmeter.

In particular, the photovoltaic parameters extracted from the J-V curves reveal an indoor PCE of 33.9 % ($V_{oc} = 4.81$ V), 32.23 % ($V_{oc} = 4.67$ V), 29.04 % ($V_{oc} = 4.18$ V), for the three illuminance levels considered. The results obtained from such measurements provide compelling evidence that the engineered PSM, which utilizes the 2D passivation strategy, demonstrates substantial potential to achieve both enhanced efficiency and high V_{oc} under low-intensity illumination conditions.

4. Conclusions

In this work we propose a perovskite post deposition treatment consisting in depositing a phenethylammonium iodide (PEAI) in 2-propanol (IPA) solution doped with 1,8-diiodooctane (DIO) on the surface of mixed-halide/mixed cation (CsFAMA) perovskite, avoiding further annealing step favoring the formation of a PEA₂PbI₄ two-dimensional overlayer. As a result, PEAI:DIO treatment has the twofold effect of passivating the iodine vacancies on the perovskite surface while modifying the electrical dipole at the CsMAFA/HTM interface, allowing for an improved hole injection/collection. This allowed us to easily scale the

cell dimension up to module level by preventing consistent power conversion efficiency (PCE) losses usually observed for perovskite-based large area devices (PSMs) under outdoor conditions. In particular, a V_{oc} approaching 17 V corresponding to a PCE of 15.58 % was achieved for a PSM with an active area of 45 cm² (composed of 15 series connected sub-cells) while a V_{oc} of 5.8 V (17.68 % PCE) was recorded for a PSM with 9 cm² active area (AA) (5 sub-cells connected in series) under 1 Sun illumination. In addition, the PEAI:DIO perovskite surface treatment has proven to be particularly effective when devices are intended to be used for indoor applications.

Indeed, under low-light conditions, hampering the effect of interfacial trap states is a way to power the device indoor PCE (iPCE). This became pivotal when large area devices designed for efficient work at solar light (employing perovskite with energy band gap < 1.7 eV) are also intended to be used in indoor conditions, where only a limited iPCE can be achieved due to the not-perfect absorbance spectral match with standard indoor illumination sources (white light emitting diodes- LED). Thanks to the PEAI:DIO 2D layer, our 9 cm² PSM exhibited an impressive V_{oc} of 4.81 V and achieved an iPCE approaching 34 % at 1000 lux (cold white LED, 6500 K), among the highest reported in literature for 1.63 eV energy band gap PSMs. Finally, long-term stability tests indicated that PEAI:DIO modified devices can face an ambient environment, regardless of the presence of an effective encapsulation. The proposed method is effective in the upscaling perovskite technology and versatile both for AM 1.5 G and indoor lights.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Francineide Lopes de Araujo: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ana Flavia Nogueira:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Aldo Di Carlo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Sara Pescetelli:** Writing – review & editing, Writing –

original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Alessia Di Vito:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Matthias Auf Der Maur:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Luigi Vesce:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Maurizio Stefanelli:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Data curation. **Antonio Agresti:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.nanoen.2025.111279](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2025.111279).

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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